

The role of capillary hysteresis and pore-scale heterogeneity in limiting the migration of buoyant immiscible fluids in porous media

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Data Set S3. Plume front position versus time (Figure 6)

Data Set S4. Estimated plume front position versus time affected by parameter variations (Figure 7).

Introduction

All the experimental and numerical results presented in Figures 2, 6 and 7 are provided as tabulated data in the text files uploaded separately. This document gives a short description of the contents of the uploaded files.

Text S1.

Tabulated data associated with Figure 2a in the manuscript are presented in Data Set S1. Experimental data and numerical model results for capillary pressure versus saturation

(indicated at the top portion of the text file as VARIABLES = "Pc (Pa)", "Wetting Phase Saturation (m^{33}/m^{33} ") are given in Data SetS1. The contents of the file include under different zones:

"Measured Primary Drainage Curve (Porous Plate)" – Measured primary drainage function for air (nonwetting) - propylene glycol (wetting) fluid pair (porous plate).

"Measured Main Wetting Curve (Porous Plate)" – Measured main wetting function for air (nonwetting) - propylene glycol (wetting) fluid pair (porous plate).

"Model Fitted to Porous Plate Data" – Results of the hysteretic capillary pressure – saturation model fitted to the primary drainage and main wetting experimental data.

"Model Used in Numerical Simulations" – Results of the hysteretic capillary pressure – saturation model used in numerical simulations

"Adjusted for Gravity Stratification (Primary Drainage)"

"Adjusted for Gravity Stratification (Main Wetting)"

"Model Fitted to Adjusted Data"

Data Set S1. Capillary pressure – saturation data for primary drainage and main imbibition processes (Figure 2a)

Text S2.

Tabulated data associated with Figure 2b in the manuscript are presented in Data SetS2. Numerical model results for estimation of relative permeability functions as a function of capillary pressure are given in the uploaded text file. The file includes tabulated data of capillary pressure, wetting relative permeability and nonwetting relative permeability.

Data Set S2. Capillary pressure – wetting phase relative permeability – nonwetting phase relative permeability for primary drainage and main imbibition processes (Figure 2b)

Text S3.

Tabulated data associated with Figure 6 in the manuscript are presented in Data SetS3. The Data Set3 contains experimental measurements of plume (nonwetting fluid) front position and numerical model predictions as a function time during the flow cell experiment (indicated at the top portion of the text file as Variables = "Time (d)" "Plume Front Position (m)" "Lower" "Upper"). "Lower" and "Upper" variables refer to lower and upper error bars in Figure 6 that are calculated based ten realization of the numerical model for the 6% parameter variation case. "Lower" and "Upper" variables are different

than zero only for the zone "6% variation-Average of 10 Realizations" in the text file.
The file contains:

"Data (this work)" – Measured plume front position (m) as a function of time (d)

"6% variation-Average of 10 Realizations" – Numerically estimated average plume front position as a function of time (d) with lower and upper error bars.

"One realization (6% variation)" – Numerically estimated plume front position (m) as a function of time (d).

Data Set S3. Plume front position versus time (Figure 6)

Text S4.

Tabulated data associated with Figure 7 in the manuscript are presented in Data SetS4. The Data Set4 contains numerical model predictions of average plume front positions as a function time for different parameter variation cases (indicated at the top portion of the text file as Variables = "Time (d)" "Plume Front Position (m)" "Lower" "Upper"). "Lower" and "Upper" variables refer to lower and upper error bars in Figure 7 to indicate variability based on the ten realizations of the numerical model for the 5.5%, 6% and 7% parameter variations. The file contains:

"5.5% variation-Average of 10 Realizations"

"6% variation-Average of 10 Realizations"

"7% variation-Average of 10 Realizations"

Data Set S4. Estimated plume front position versus time affected by parameter variations (Figure 7).